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SUPPORTING CAPACITY OF REGIONAL ORIGINAL INCOME AND GROSS REGIONAL DOMESTIC PRODUCT TOWARDS GOVERNMENT CAPITAL EXPENDITURE OF WEST NUSA TENGGARA PROVINCE

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the carrying capacity of local revenue and gross regional domestic product on capital expenditure in the province of West Nusa Tenggara, both partially and simultaneously. This study uses 10-year data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. The analysis method used is Multiple Linear Regression Analysis processed with SPSS. The results of this study indicate that partially the Local Revenue variable has a significant effect on Capital Expenditure of West Nusa Tenggara Province during the 2013-2022 period, while the Gross Regional Domestic Product variable does not have a significant effect on Capital Expenditure of West Nusa Tenggara Province during the 2013-2022 period. Simultaneously, the Local Revenue and Gross Regional Domestic Product variables do not have a significant effect on the Capital Expenditure of West Nusa Tenggara Province during the 2013-2022 period.

Keywords: *Original Regional Income, Regional Gross Domestic Product, West Nusa Tenggara*

INTRODUCTION

The economic development support of a nation cannot be separated from the financial support and natural resources and human resources contained in a country. Sources of state revenue come from the central government and from regional revenue sources, each region in Indonesia's original regional income is obtained from revenue from the management of developing economic

sectors and contributes to regional income. Government revenues reflected in the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget are obtained from several sectors, especially the tax sector and other economic sources, both from agricultural products, mining and so on.

According to (Badrudin 2017: 98) original regional income (PAD) is all regional income originating from original regional economic sources in accordance with statutory regulations. PAD sources from local regional taxes, regional levies, portions of regional business profits, and other income that is legitimate according to law. In 2018, the PAD target was IDR 1,767,746,421,040 with a realization of IDR 1,660,417,707,372, (93.93%) in that year, the PAD figure decreased because an earthquake occurred in all districts and cities in West Nusa Tenggara so that on average the buildings in NTB were damaged.

Economic development is inseparable from the government's performance in implementing development programs that have been stated in the 5-year regional development plan, usually when the head of government changes. is. The implementation of this development program is targeted to improve the welfare of the community, especially in the province of West Nusa Tenggara, and what needs to be considered in order to achieve programs in improving people's welfare is that government performance must be good and free from budget misuse.

The extent to which regional development programs are run by the provincial government is very dependent on the achievement of activities in all economic sectors, which has an impact on the level of community prosperity. One indicator of the level of prosperity of the population in an area/region can be seen from the GRDP value. According to Firdaus (2013), GRDP is the total added value generated by all economic activities in a region in a certain time. The increase in GRDP is caused by the increase in the production of goods and services (Silvia, 2013). Economic development in all sectors is seen from the role of Regional Original Income to fund potential economic sectors that can open up employment opportunities and increase the role of these sectors in spurring economic growth rates between sectors in the region. Indicators of regional development achievements can be seen from two sides, namely regional original income and gross regional domestic product. As the results of Handayani's research, it shows that there is no influence of regional original income and gross regional domestic product on government capital expenditure (Handayani, 2022), in several GRDP sectors in Central Java Province.

This study aims to analyze the influence of the carrying capacity of Regional Original Income and Gross Regional Domestic Product partially and simultaneously on the Capital Expenditure of the West Nusa Tenggara Provincial Government.

Research Objectives

As an illustration in this study that the objectives of this study are to analyze the carrying capacity of regional original income and gross regional domestic product and their influence on capital expenditure both partially and simultaneously.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Regional Income

Regional income is all regional rights that are recognized as an increase in net wealth value in the relevant budget year period, and are a source of regional income that comes from Regional Original Income (PAD), Balancing Funds, and Other Legitimate Regional Income.

Further Explanation:

Regional income is an important component in the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD) and is used to finance the implementation of regional government and development.

Regional income can come from various types of income, which are generally divided into three large groups:

1. Regional Original Income (PAD):

PAD is income that comes from the potential of the region itself. PAD includes:

Regional Taxes: For example, motor vehicle tax, hotel tax, restaurant tax, etc.

Regional Retribution: Payment for services or permits provided by the regional government.

Results of Separated Regional Asset Management: For example, a portion of the profit from a regional company.

Other Legitimate PAD: Regional income other than taxes, levies, and results of separated regional asset management.

2. Balancing Fund:

Balancing fund is a fund sourced from the APBN allocated to regions to fund regional needs in the context of implementing decentralization. Balancing funds include:

Revenue Sharing Fund (DBH): Funds sourced from tax revenues and natural resources.

General Allocation Fund (DAU): Funds allocated for equalizing financial capacity between regions.

Special Allocation Fund (DAK): Funds allocated for special activities that are national priorities.

3. Other Legitimate Regional Income:

This income includes grants, emergency funds, and other legitimate income according to laws and regulations.

Thus, regional income has an important role in supporting regional autonomy and realizing community welfare through financing various government and development affairs.

The definition of carrying capacity is the total income capacity owned by individuals, private companies, entrepreneurs and the government to carry out all planned activities to achieve a goal.

Definition of Capital Expenditure

According to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), capital expenditure is an expenditure used for the purchase/procurement or construction of tangible fixed assets with a useful value of more than one year. The formation of these assets includes the procurement of land, heavy equipment, transportation equipment, workshop equipment, agricultural equipment, office equipment and supplies, computers, kitchen equipment, room decorations, studio equipment, communication equipment, measuring instruments, medical equipment, laboratory equipment, road construction, bridges, water networks, street lighting, parks and city forests, electricity and telephone installations, buildings, books/libraries, art objects, procurement of animals/livestock and plants, and weapons/security. Capital expenditure is classified into Routine expenditure and Development expenditure.

According to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), capital expenditure is an expenditure used for the purchase/procurement or construction of tangible fixed assets whose utility value is more than one year. The formation of these assets includes the procurement of land, heavy equipment, transportation equipment, workshop equipment, agricultural equipment, office equipment and supplies, computers, kitchen equipment, room decorations, studio equipment, communication equipment, measuring instruments,

medical equipment, laboratory equipment, road construction, bridges, water networks, street lighting, parks and city forests, electricity and telephone installations, buildings, books/libraries, art objects, procurement of animals/livestock and plants, and weapons/security. Capital expenditure is classified into routine expenditure and development expenditure.

RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in this study is a quantitative descriptive method with variables of local revenue, gross regional domestic product and capital expenditure variables.

This study is a case study conducted in West Nusa Tenggara Province using secondary data for ten years, namely from 2013 to 2022.

The location of this study is in West Nusa Tenggara Province, with geographical reasons because there are characteristics of the islands that require different handling to improve their development.

This study uses time series data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) of West Nusa Tenggara Province in 2013-2022 which is measured in percentage form. The analysis technique used is linear regression analysis multiple regression, classical assumption test, and hypothesis test.

1. Multiple Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a statistical technique that is useful for examining and modeling the relationship between variables. The multiple linear regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2$$

Where:

Y = Capital Expenditure

a = Constant

b = Coefficient

X₁ = Regional Original Income

X₂ = Gross Regional Domestic Product

2. Classical Assumption Test

Classical assumptions are made to determine the validity of the regression equation formed.

a. Normality Test

By conducting a statistical test, if the significant value is greater than $\alpha = 5\%$ or 0.05, it can be concluded that the residual in the regression model follows a normal distribution.

b. Multicollinearity Test

If the VIF value of each independent variable is less than 10, the regression model is free from multicollinearity problems.

c. Autocorrelation Test

If the calculated value of d is greater than the du Durbin-Watson table and less than 4-du ($du < d < 4-du$), then it can be said that the regression model used is free from autocorrelation problems.

d. Heteroscedasticity Test

A regression model is said to not contain heteroscedasticity if the probability of significance is above the 5% confidence level.

3. Hypothesis Test

a. Partial Test (t Test)

If the calculated t value $< t$ table, it is concluded that there is no significant influence of variable x on y and if conversely t calculated $> t$ table, there is a significant influence of variable x on y.

b. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

If the calculated F value $< F$ table, it is concluded that there is no significant influence of variable x on y and if conversely F calculated $> F$ table, there is a significant influence of variable x on y.

DISCUSSION RESULTS

General Overview of the Region

West Nusa Tenggara Province is one of the provinces in Indonesia, located in the central part of the Nusa Tenggara Islands. West Nusa Tenggara Province consists of 2 (two) large islands, namely Lombok Island and Sumbawa Island and hundreds of small islands. The area of West Nusa Tenggara Province reaches 20,153.20 km². Located between 115.46 - 119.5 East Longitude and 8.10 - 9.5 'South Latitude, with a population of 5.41 million people. The area of Sumbawa Island reaches 15,426.20 km² (76.50%) or 2/3 of the area of West Nusa Tenggara Province, and the area of Lombok Island only reaches 1/3. Lombok Island consists of four districts and city governments including East Lombok Regency, Central Lombok Regency, West Lombok Regency, North Lombok Regency and Mataram City. The provincial capital is in the city of Mataram which is the center of government, the center of education and the center of trade serving the islands of Lombok and Sumbawa. Meanwhile, Sumbawa Island consists of four districts and cities, namely Bima City, Bima Regency, Dompu Regency, Sumbawa Regency and West Sumbawa Regency. The infrastructure built by the regional government with the support of the central government has been able to connecting these two islands so that the flow of goods and services can be reached easily even across islands, namely the island of Bali and the island of East Nusa Tenggara. How this infrastructure development is inseparable from the ability of the region to reap regional income which will be used as capital expenditure.

In the analysis of the influence of regional original income on capital expenditure, it can be seen in the following analyst data:

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-45.017	68.766		-.655	.534
	PAD	1.393	.731	.549	1.906	.098
	PDRB	.507	.496	.294	1.021	.341

Based on the results of the analysis above, the following multiple linear regression analysis formula was obtained:

$$Y = -45.017 + 1.393X_1 + 0.507 X_2 + e$$

The results of the analysis obtained that the Constant of -45.01 percent states that if the Regional Original Income (X₁) and Gross

Regional Domestic Product (X2) are zero (0) then the level of Capital Expenditure (Y) is -45.01 percent, the regression coefficient of Regional Original Income (X1) is 1.39 percent shows that if the original regional income increases by 1%, it causes capital expenditure to increase by 1.39 percent. Likewise, conversely, if the original regional income decreases by 1%, capital expenditure decreases by 1.39 percent, and the regression coefficient of Gross Regional Domestic Product (X2) is 0.50 percent, indicating that if the gross regional domestic product increases by 1%, it causes capital expenditure to decrease by 0.50 percent. Likewise, conversely, if the gross regional domestic product decreases by 1%, capital expenditure increases by 0.50 percent.

Classical Assumption Test

a. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test	
	Unstandardized Residual
N	10

b. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	45.017	68.766		.655	.534		
	PAD	1.393	.731	.549	1.906	.098	.982	1.018
	PDRB	.507	.496	.294	1.021	.341	.982	1.018

a. Dependent Variable: BM

The results of the multicollinearity test for research from 2013-2022 in West Nusa Tenggara Province, it can be seen that the Tolerance value of the independent variables, namely Regional Original Income (X1) is 0.982 and Gross Regional Domestic Product (X2) is 0.982. From the Tolerance value of the two independent variables, it is more than 0.1. And the VIF value of Regional Original Income (X1) is 1.018 and Gross Regional Domestic Product (X2) is 1.018. From the VIF value of the two independent variables, it is less than 10. So it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

a. Autocorrelation Test

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.656 ^a	.430	.268	10.59420	2.115

a. Predictors: (Constant), PDRB, PAD

b. Dependent Variable: BM

The results of the Autocorrelation test can be seen from the Durbin-Watson value of 2.115 so that the du value = 1.6413 and the dl value = 0.6972 are obtained. Therefore, a test can be carried out 4-dl = 4-0.6972 = 3.3028 and the 4-du value = 4-1.6413 = 2.3587 so that it can be seen from the du value <dw <4-du (1.6413

Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	9.34321036
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.160
	Positive	.110
	Negative	-.160
Test Statistic		.160
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c, d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

To ensure that the residual data is normal, the residual data is retested using the Kolomorov Smirnov test. The table shows that the Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed) value is greater than 0.05, which is 0.200. Thus, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

<2.115 <2.3587). So the Durbin-Watson test value obtained is 2.115 which is between the upper limit of du (1.6413) and 2.3587 (4-du) so that the decision maker accepts H0 which means that there is no autocorrelation.

Uji Hipotesis

partial test (Uji t)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-45.017	68.766		-.655	.534
	PAD	1.393	.731	.549	1.906	.098
	PDRB	.507	.496	.294	1.021	.341

a. Dependent Variable: BM

The Influence of Local Original Income (X1) on Capital Expenditure (Y)

Based on the results of the t-count value on the Local Original Income variable (X1), the t-count value obtained was 1.906 with a t table of 2.262, so the t-count value <t table. While the significant value on the local original income variable is 0.098 > 0.05. So it

can be concluded that H_a is rejected and H_0 is accepted, meaning that the level of local original income does not have a significant effect on capital expenditure. This means that the Local Original Income in West Nusa Tenggara Province has not been able to meet the needs for Capital Expenditure in West Nusa Tenggara Province.

The Influence of Gross Regional Domestic Product (X2) on Capital Expenditure (Y)

Based on the results of the t-count value on the Gross Regional Domestic Product variable, the t-count value obtained was 2.262 with a t table of 1.859, so the t-count value $< t$ table. While the significant value of the gross regional domestic product variable is $0.341 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that H_a is rejected and H_0 is accepted, meaning that Gross Regional Domestic Product does not have a significant effect on Capital Expenditure. This means that Gross Regional Domestic Product in West Nusa Tenggara Province has not been able to increase Capital Expenditure, due to the lack of income received by the region to be spent by the local government.

b. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	593.692	2	296.846	2.645	.139 ^b
	Residual	785.660	7	112.237		
	Total	1379.352	9			
a. Dependent Variable: BM						
Predictors: (Constant), PDRB, PAD						

Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the F count value is 2.645 percent and the sig value is 0.139. So in this study, the F count value $< F$ table ($2.645 < 4.74$) and the sig value $0.139 > 0.05$ were obtained. So it can be concluded that the H_2 hypothesis test is rejected and H_0 is accepted. This explains that regional original income and gross regional domestic product simultaneously (together) do not have a significant effect on the capital expenditure of the West Nusa Tenggara Provincial Government.

Discussion Results

The Effect of Regional Original Income (PAD) and Gross Regional Domestic Product (PDRB) on Government Capital Expenditure.

1. The Effect of Regional Original Income on Capital Expenditure

The results of the first hypothesis test show that the regression direction coefficient of the Regional Original Income variable (X1) is 0.731 or positive, so it can be said that the Regional Original Income (PAD) variable does not have a significant effect on Capital Expenditure (BM).

Based on the results of the t-test on the Regional Original Income variable (X1), the t-value obtained is 1.906 with a t table of 2.262, so the t-value is $< t$ table. While the significant value of the regional original income variable is $0.098 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that H_a is rejected and H_0 is accepted, meaning that the level of regional original income does not have a significant effect on

capital expenditure. This means that the Regional Original Income in West Nusa Tenggara Province has not been able to meet the needs for Capital Expenditure in West Nusa Tenggara Province.

According to Nopitasari (2017: 56) states that Regional Original Income (PAD) is income obtained by regions that is collected based on regional regulations in accordance with laws and regulations. Regional Original Income (PAD) as a source of regional revenue itself needs to be increased so that it can bear part of the burden of spending needed for the implementation of government and development activities which increase every year so that broad, real and responsible regional autonomy independence can be implemented.

2. The Effect of Gross Regional Domestic Product on Capital Expenditure

The results of the first hypothesis test show that the regression direction coefficient of the Gross Regional Domestic Product variable (X2) is 0.496 or positive, so it can be said that the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) variable has a negative effect on Capital Expenditure (BM). Based on the results of the t-count value on the Gross Regional Domestic Product variable, the t-count value obtained is 0.765 with a t table of 1.859, so the t-count value $< t$ table. While the significant value on the gross regional domestic product variable is $0.469 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that H_2 is rejected and H_0 is accepted, meaning that Gross Regional Domestic Product does not have a significant effect on Capital Expenditure.

According to Nopitasari (2017: 57) it was concluded that there was no significant effect of Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) on Capital Expenditure (BM), so the hypothesis proposed was not proven. This means that the Gross Regional Domestic Product in West Nusa Tenggara Province has not been able to increase Capital Expenditure, due to the lack of income received by the region for

spent by the local government. This does not mean that the management of local government expenditure related to the allocation of capital expenditure, GRDP is not the main reference in the process of preparing the APBD and capital expenditure allocation, but there are a number of certain factors that influence it, for example the process of preparing the general budget policy (KUA) every year which in addition to paying attention to regional economic conditions but also socio-political conditions in the region.

The results of this study support the research of Nopitasi (2017), Ermiwati (2021), which states that there is no influence between Capital Expenditure on increasing Gross Regional Domestic Product.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion that have been explained in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that There is no significant influence of Regional Original Income on Capital Expenditure "can be accepted. This is based on multiple linear regression analysis (t-test) It is known that the calculated t value is 1.906 with a t table of 2.262, then the calculated t value $< t$ table or $1.906 < 2.262$ and a significant value of $0.098 > 0.05$.

There is no significant influence of Gross Regional Domestic Product on Capital Expenditure" cannot be accepted. This is based on multiple linear regression analysis (t-test) it is known that the calculated t value is 1.021 with a t-table value of 2.262, then the calculated t value $< t$ -table or $1.021 < 2.262$ and a significant value

of $0.341 > 0.05$, and the results of the determination coefficient test (R^2) of 43% indicate that the influence of the magnitude of Regional Original Income and Gross Regional Domestic Product together on Capital Expenditure while the rest is influenced by other variables that are not studied such as Revenue Sharing Funds, General Allocation Funds, and Special Allocation Funds.

West Nusa Tenggara Province needs to explore sources of GRDP and development of leading sectors so that regional income increasingly increasing, which can be used to finance priority sectors in advancing the regional economy of West Nusa Tenggara and increasing economic growth. as well as the provision of facilities and infrastructure in the context of developing regional development and economy.

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